

EXTRACTION OF IRON FROM COPPER SMELTER WASTE

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Abstract: The article presents the results of research on the technology of extraction of ferrous metals from concentrator waste. Accordingly, based on the analysis of local and foreign literature on the processing of concentrators, the classical pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical technologies for the separation of iron and its compounds from the waste were studied and their advantages and disadvantages were identified. Copper production has been shown to generate large amounts of oxidized waste during flotation enrichment of sulfide copper-molybdenum ores and after magnetic enrichment of iron ores. Chemical analysis of the waste showed that it contained large amounts of oxidized iron compounds.

Key words: Copper, waste, concentrate, flotation, slag, coke, solution, cake, sulfuric acid, leaching, charge.

Introduction: The analysis of world copper production and its consumption shows rapid growth, if at the beginning of the 20th century copper production was 0.4 mln. was a little more than tons, but at the beginning of the 21st century it exceeded 21 million tons.[4] At the same time, the decrease in the amount of copper in the ore from 0.5-5% in the last century to 0.20-0.40% at the present time leads to an increase in the comprehensive use of raw materials, the use of resource and energy-saving technologies using man-made waste of metallurgical production, the development of science paying special attention to integration with output is a topical issue today. In this regard, the copper industry in developed countries is paying special attention to new technologies that allow to significantly expand the base of raw materials by extracting valuable components from man-made waste. In the world, scientific research in the field of non-ferrous metallurgy is aimed at involving industrial man-

made waste in the main production in order to increase the production of non-ferrous metals. It should be noted that the production of copper is associated with the release of a large amount of man-made waste, which is much higher than the amount of copper produced.[3.5.] Wastes from concentrators, man-made wastes, copper slags and gases from the smelting of sulphide copper concentrates are produced. The scientific research conducted in the field of copper production in our republic is focused on the development of technology for the processing of metallurgical slag, dust and man-made waste containing metal. [8]

Literature review: In world practice, a large number of studies have been conducted on the extraction of valuable components from metallurgical production waste, in particular, A.N. Zelikman, G.I. Gazaleeva, S.V. Mamonov, E.V. Bratygin, A.M. Klyushnikov, M.N. Sabanova, T.M. Vovnova, B.P. Rudnev, A.R. Bakirov, D. Yu. Voronin, L. A. Voropanova, A. V. Vanyukov, V. Yu. Gusev, V. Ya. Zaitsev, M. G. Sagdieva, K. S. Sanakulov, S.A. Abdurakhmanov, A.S. Khasanov, M.M. Yakubov and others paid attention. [1] As a result of the conducted research, it was found that in the complex extraction of valuable components from the technological waste of copper production, one of the difficult problems is related to the composition of many components with similar properties, which leads to the difficulty of their selective extraction. [2] At the same time, scientific and research work is being carried out on the improvement of technological processes aimed at the use of technological waste in order to extract valuable components for the main technological production. There is a lot of information in the literature about the possibilities of processing technological waste, using them as sources of metals, but there is very little information about the extraction of valuable components and their additional separation from technological waste. This direction is currently becoming more relevant in the creation of new high-yield technologies in copper metallurgy.[6.7.]

Research Methodology: 1) Preparation of slides: A Struers Labopol-5 semi-automatic machine for preparing metallographic samples with Laboforce equipment was used for preparing the slides. The rotation speed of the grinding wheel is adjustable and 0-500 rpm. The range of pressing force of grinders: 0-40 N. Interchangeable sanders and grinding discs are fixed by means of a magnet. Samples are cast in epoxy resin, (1.3 and 9 μm) surface is polished on Struers grinding wheels with different dispersion diamond grinding.

2) Light microscopy: Light microscopy was used to obtain a general understanding of the structure of the samples, porosity, sulfide distribution, and preparation for solution microscopy studies. For these studies, an Olympus GX71F-5

microscope, equipped with a high-quality image processing system, zooming from 12.5 to 1000 times, was used.

1-Picture. Light microscope Olympus GX71F-5

Analysis and results: The highest level of recovery from waste was achieved at 20% consumption of regenerant, at 900-1000 °C temperature and 120 minutes isothermal holding in slag waste recovery.

2-Picture. At different temperatures: (a) 600 °C; (b) 800 °C; (c) 900 °C; (d) Photographs of 1000 °C regenerated granular particles

6 samples of the least, intermediate and high levels of recovery were selected for further research. These samples were subjected to additional crushing and magnetic separation in a laboratory mill. [9] The obtained high-grade metallized product was remelted in a laboratory furnace at $t=1500^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an inert atmosphere, and the obtained metal alloy was analyzed for its main components. Picture 2 presents pictures of samples recovered at different temperatures. Granular particles regenerated at 1000°C showed the best physico-mechanical properties, such as dense surface, good strength and high antioxidant properties (Picture 2). However, at a further increase in temperature (1200°C), the recovered precipitates coalesce and become semi-melts, which interferes with normal operation under industrial conditions. For example, in the case of a rotary kiln, which is a typical equipment for the recovery of metals such as nickel and iron, the heated material easily adheres to the wall of the rotary kiln, which can cause difficulties in the smooth passage of the recovered material. In addition, after the samples were quenched with water, the sample recovered at 1200°C is easily oxidized in the environment. [10] Based on these results, the optimal

recovery temperature was determined to be 1000°C [2; s. 404-413]. The effect of coal dosage on the reduction was investigated in mass ratios of coal: 15–25% of the sample (according to the carbon content of the coal 15% of coal in the reaction was 0.9 times higher than theoretical).

The influence of isothermal storage time for waste on the level of recovery was determined in laboratory experiments at the following dimensions: temperature 900-1000°C, recovery consumption in the amount of 20% of the mass of ferrous waste and slag, isothermal storage time 90, 120 minutes. [11] The amount of iron in the concentrate increased with increasing recovery time and reached a peak after 120 min, while the extraction was almost unchanged. The optimal time to ensure the high quality of the concentrate was determined to be 120 minutes.

1-diagram. The effect of the consumption of the regenerating substance on the recovery process

Tablet 1.

Consumption of the restorative substance

Recovery cost, %	Temperature, C	Magnetic fraction %	Non-magnetic fraction %
5	900	74	26
10	900	80,2	19,8
15	900	81,3	18,7
20	900	82	18
25	900	84,3	15,7
30	900	84,3	15,7

Conclusion/Recommendations: 1) FeO , Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4 contained in the wastes of the copper beneficiation factory were reduced to iron by restorative incineration;
2) Using a magnetic separator, a magnetic fraction was obtained from the soot;
3. The non-magnetic fraction was selectively dissolved in sulfuric acid and precipitation of the metals contained in the solution was achieved using the cementation method;
4. As a result of selective melting, it was possible to extract gold and silver metals from the solid cake that did not melt;

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